

Toward Calibrated Trust: What Working Scientists Need from an AI Co-Scientist

Johanna Cohoon^{1*}, Elisha Wood-Charlson¹, Sarah Poon¹, Ben Allen², Hans Carlson¹, Mikaela Cashman¹, Romy Chakraborty¹, John-Marc Chandonia¹, Mingfei Chen¹, Nick Chia³, Robert Cottingham², Markus de Raad¹, Gui de Siqueira¹, Adam Deutschbauer¹, Janaka Edirisinghe³, Thomas Eng¹, José Faria³, Andrew Freiburger³, Tian Gu³, Nomi Harris¹, Chris Henry³, Jake Hillzinger⁴, Dan Hopp², Ruiwen Hu¹, Milo Johnson⁴, Roy Kamimura¹, Ulas Karaoz¹, Ahmed Khan¹, Dileep Kishore², Hira Lesea¹, Lauren Lui¹, Filipe Liu³, David Lyon¹, Gazi Mahmud¹, Gianna Marschmann¹, Mark A Miller¹, Shekhar Mishra¹, Aindrila Mukhopadhyay¹, Chris Neely¹, Avery Noonan¹, Kate O'Grady¹, Peter Osborne¹, Gavin Price¹, Priya Ranjan², Jacob Rapp¹, Justin Reese¹, Bill Riehl¹, Boris Sadkhin³, Rekha Seshadri¹, Swetha Suresh Kumar², Jing Tao¹, Gwyneth Terry¹, Mitch Thompson¹, Susannah Tringe¹, Surya Tripathi⁴, Ben Weinberg¹, Pamela Weisenhorn³, Yuguo Yang¹, Adam Arkin¹, Christopher Mungall¹, Paramvir Dehal¹

¹Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, Berkeley, CA, USA, ²Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, TN, USA, ³Argonne National Laboratory, Lemont, IL, USA, ⁴University of California Berkeley, Berkeley, CA, USA

* Corresponding author, hcohoon@lbl.gov

Zenodo link: <https://zenodo.org/records/20595967>

Abstract

The Biology and Environmental Research (BER) Intelligence Layer (BERIL, <https://beril-doe.org/>) provides an AI agent interaction layer on top of the DOE Systems Biology Knowledgebase (KBase, kbase.us)'s new data lakehouse architecture. BERIL is an agentic co-scientist environment that scientists can use to discover data and carry out research projects. Success in this new mode of scientific work requires an understanding of how researchers will interact with agentic co-scientists. Here, we present findings from interviews with 11 BER scientists who used BERIL's co-scientist to work with data in the KBase Lakehouse during a one-day workshop. Across the board, the agent's analytical capability was rarely the limiting factor; the harder challenge was for scientists to stay in command of the collaboration: maintaining a mental model of the co-scientist's process, judging what to trust, and deciding when to verify. BERIL's ability to access the KBase data lakehouse and integrate that data with other sources emerged as its key enabling strength. Because BER scientists already have established preferences for certain AI agents and skills, this capability is a key asset that distinguishes BERIL from other co-scientist systems and increases its effectiveness for researchers across the DOE landscape and beyond. Results also pointed to opportunities for supporting users' mental models of BERIL's actions and for helping them calibrate their trust in the co-scientist. Together, our findings indicate the importance of meeting users where they are, considering their needs and expectations as we introduce new tooling to accelerate their scientific workflows.

Introduction

Scientific research is entering a new paradigm where researchers are using artificial intelligence (AI) agents as tools in their workflows. The integration of new AI “co-scientist” systems has already been widely accepted as the future of science. In May 2026, *Nature* published a cluster of multi-agent “co-scientist” systems that generate hypotheses, propose experiments, and analyze data (1–3). Although the technology is changing rapidly, some known limitations include:

- Access to data and metadata: Most biological data is siloed across non-standardized repositories and deposited without key contextual features (i.e., environmental / experimental context)
- Accuracy and reliability: Agent hallucination remains a concern for retaining scientific integrity
- Traceability and provenance: Co-scientists don’t always clearly report which datasets were used and combined, which intermediate products were created, and what computation was performed on these
- Scientists/co-scientist interactions: While frictions are evident, it is yet unclear what training and user experience improvements are needed to achieve more effective, productive human / technology interactions

The scientist/co-scientist interaction is currently the least well understood limitation. Most evaluations to date examine agent output in isolation rather than the scientist–agent interaction over the course of real research. The ability of these systems to perform sophisticated analytic workflows is no longer a blocker for many research tasks (4): agentic co-scientists now generate hypotheses, design analyses, and interpret data well enough to pass peer review in narrow settings (1,2,5). While there is much to improve regarding these analytical aspects, the human side of the partnership is equally important. These systems are evaluated largely on autonomy or benchmark accuracy, yet in every reported success – humans framed the problem and checked the output. A recent *Nature* editorial argues that this human role is a feature of good science, not a temporary scaffold (6). Because agents can be confidently wrong (i.e., hallucinate) and misinterpret what they did in ways invisible in the finished product, users must examine traces in detail to ferret out mistakes (7). On genuinely complex tasks, humans still outperform the best agents (8,9). An open question is how working scientists can calibrate their reliance on AI so that they trust the partner only so far as the system’s capabilities warrant (10). How does the operator know when to delegate, when to verify, and how to hold on to enough of a mental model of the agent’s process to understand and trust the results?

Technical solutions can improve output quality, theoretically increasing the likelihood of tool adoption by improving perceived usefulness (11). Provenance and reasoning traces give scientists something to inspect. But these artefacts can be overwhelming, especially when presented in raw form, and, as we observe below, this can lead to disengagement or falling back on intuition or prior expectations. This report initiates an investigation of these issues with a new co-scientist, the Biology and Environmental Research (BER) Intelligence Layer (BERIL, <https://beril-doe.org/>), on a governed, fully traceable data and execution substrate (the KBase Lakehouse). We represent a community of biological scientists that pursued our individual

research questions over a single day with the BERIL co-scientist; we report what shaped our abilities to understand, steer, and correct research developed alongside this “partner.”

In this report, we share findings from interviews conducted throughout the process of using the BERIL co-scientist during the workshop organized and after. Below, we describe the workshop and our research approach before presenting key themes emergent from our interviews. Our findings provide insights into how AI agents for science can be integrated into established research workflows.

Background

BERIL was deployed as an agentic co-scientist on top of the DOE Systems Biology Knowledgebase (KBase, kbase.us)’s new lakehouse architecture. This architecture enables several key features. First, the KBase Lakehouse is a biological data integration platform where users can bring their own data and immediately explore the context of their data among all of the other public user data and core public biological reference databases (e.g., NCBI RefSeq, GTDB, PDB, UniProt/UniRef, etc). The KBase Lakehouse supports data sharing, tracks full provenance of all data sources and transformations, and enables new knowledge to be immediately accessible to the community. Second, BERIL captures full agent traces alongside research outputs (reports, tables, figures, etc.), which links all resource outputs to agentic sources, code, and decisions. The linking of these infrastructures is critical for trustworthy, robust, and cumulative analyses that support the DOE BER missions of advancing environmental plant and microbial biology, bioenergy, biomanufacturing and materials, critical minerals, supply-chain resilience, and health security.

To explore how our research community reacts to and interacts with a co-scientist, we organized a one-day “KBase/BERIL Co-scientist Paper Challenge” workshop for 38 researchers from three DOE National Laboratories and one university, so we could explore how far one might get toward a publishable artifact in a single day. The workshop was organized so that an engaged and AI-curious community of biological science researchers could access public data via the KBase Lakehouse and/or upload their own data for analysis, and explore, analyze, and make conclusions about the data using the BERIL co-scientist, alongside full reasoning traces. The goal was to understand how BER scientists would work alongside an agentic co-scientist and what impressions they would have of the system.

Workshop overview

BER researchers were invited to pursue a research question with BERIL, seeing how far they could advance toward a satisfactory manuscript draft. As part of the workshop registration process, researchers shared proposed paper topic ideas, which ranged from understanding biochemical processes in single microbial cells, exploring microbial evolution across gene families or shifts in environment, and leveraging microbial function to understand cycling of nutrients in the environment or production of target biomolecules in bioreactors.

The workshop had a hybrid format such that participants across three sites could join in discussion as a group (in person / Zoom) and work locally as a group at their remote site. Announcements were given both in person and over Zoom. The workshop began at 9:00am Pacific Time, starting with an overview of the KBase Lakehouse and BERIL integration and a pre-workshop questionnaire that explored how the community viewed the concept of an AI co-scientist before we started, including: how effective would the co-scientist be at tasks like ideation, hypothesis generation, experimental design, etc.; how reliable and trustworthy the co-scientist would be; how easy/difficult exploring an idea would be; and how often people already use AI tools for their research tasks.

Throughout the workshop, researchers were prompted to fill out time-stamped questionnaires that tracked changes in how they viewed the co-scientist and some people participated in short interviews (30 minutes or less). At the end, we had a long group discussion about the experience, paired with a final post-workshop questionnaire to capture final changes in perception. In the two weeks following the event, we conducted additional 1-hr follow-up interviews. This report provides an initial evaluation of the interview feedback, with the goal of highlighting key factors necessary for effective, productive human/agent interactions.

Methods

Questionnaire data was collected before, during, and after the workshop from consenting co-authors. We also captured logs of consenting workshop attendees' interactions with BERIL. In this report, however, we focus on the interviews conducted during and after the workshop. Data analysis of questionnaire responses, interviews, and systems logs is ongoing.

Researcher Recruitment

Biological science researchers were recruited by email invitation from KBase staff, with the goal of incorporating representation from the major DOE BER data platforms, Science Focus Areas, and Bioenergy Research Centers at Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, and associated University of California, Berkeley, programs. Researchers from Argonne and Oak Ridge National Laboratories were also recruited by local KBase staff to encourage a diversity of research topics. In total, 38 people joined to test out the co-scientist and 20+ additional people attended in person or virtually to observe, provide technical support, or help co-host the workshop. All workshop attendees are co-authors on this manuscript.

The scientists had a broad range of professional experience; it was most common to have 6-10 years of experience (see Figure 1). It was most common among participating co-authors to report using AI daily for research tasks (see Figure 2).

Figure 1. Workshop participating co-authors self-reported professional experience

Figure 2. Frequency of AI use for research tasks among participating co-authors (self reported via survey)

To provide further context about how interviewees compared to all workshop attendees, we include data on all participants' self-reported post-workshop confidence in the BERIL co-scientist (see Figure 3) and on interviewees' responses (see Table 1). As in the broader workshop population, interviewees most commonly "somewhat agreed" that they were confident in the co-scientist. And, like the broader workshop population, interviewees most commonly reported that they use AI for research tasks daily. To preserve privacy, we do not report interviewees' professional experience at an individual level; however, interviewees did represent all levels of experience from 0-2 years to 21+ years.

Table 1. Interviewees' frequency of AI use and post-workshop confidence

Person ID	Frequency of AI use	Post-event agreement with "I am confident in the AI co-scientist"
P1*	Daily (reported in interview)	(no response)
P2*#	Daily	Strongly disagree
P3*	Daily	Somewhat agree
P4*	Daily	Somewhat disagree
P5*	A few times per week	Somewhat agree
P6#	Daily	Neither agree nor disagree
P7#	Daily	Somewhat agree
P8#	Daily	Somewhat agree
P9#	A few times per week	Somewhat agree
P10#	Daily	Strongly disagree
P11*	Daily (reported in interview)	Somewhat agree

**participated in extended interview #participated in brief interview*

Figure 3. Post-event agreement among participating co-authors with "I am confident in the AI co-scientist"

Interviews

In the afternoon of the workshop, participating scientists were invited to give brief interviews. Six co-authors agreed. Three researchers conducted these interviews, recording the conversations (ranging 8:46 to 28:52 minutes). Following the event, everyone was invited to provide longer interviews; six people agreed, including one person who had given a brief interview during the workshop. One researcher conducted these interviews and recorded them (44:57 to 55:16 minutes).

The brief interviews discussed any routines established during the day and helpful strategies employed, reflections on how the co-scientist is engaging with them, and any surprising interactions between themselves and the co-scientist.

Extended post-event interviews discussed:

- How their usual research process compares to their experience with the co-scientist
- Their degree of involvement in the research process during the workshop
- Notable experiences with the co-scientist and their general impressions
- Their relationship with the co-scientist
- The co-scientist's limitations
- Their expectations for how publishing and collaboration may change in future
- Followup questions based on questionnaire responses before/during/after the event

Analysis approach

To analyze the interview data, one author applied thematic analysis (12). This qualitative analysis technique is used to identify “patterns across an (entire) data set” (12). When conducting thematic analysis, researchers label their data (e.g., quotes from interviews) and iteratively revise and combine these labels to construct themes in a process referred to as coding. “Codes identify a feature of the data. . . that appears interesting to the analyst” (12).

The author performing the analysis reviewed all transcripts. Then, working one interview at a time, they coded these transcripts by pasting quotes and paragraph summaries with time stamps into virtual sticky notes that were clustered according to the code applied (see Figure 4). Sticky notes were color coded to indicate which interviewee yielded the data it represented. Initially, codes were high level and abstract (e.g., “mistrust”), but as more data was added to the analysis, more detailed codes were applied or replaced old ones (e.g., “no signals of lack of confidence; difficult to interpret” was added under the “mistrust” code).

Throughout analysis, the analyst returned to interview transcripts to confirm understanding and reorganized quotes and their codes to better represent the data. She wrote memos on her thoughts to make hazy ideas more concrete, noting trends spotted and the data that support them. Via this iterative process, she identified higher order themes that were composed of clusters of codes and the data they represented. Each theme represents a “patterned response” and thus captures common sentiments among interviewees (12).

Before completing thematic analysis, the analyst discussed the findings with the workshop organizers, giving that research team the opportunity to prioritize findings, make further revisions, and provide additional insights. Workshop attendees were given the opportunity to suggest edits to this initial report, understanding that additional analyses will augment the interview findings in follow-on reports.

Figure 4. A screenshot from early in the thematic analysis process

Results

Through our analysis, we identified four interrelated themes in the interview data that specifically relate to the human/co-scientist interaction, which we felt would be of interest to the broader community and provide guidance on how to design for human/co-scientist engagement. Here we summarize those, illustrating our findings with examples from our data. These results provide insight into how AI agents for science can best be integrated into established workflows. Quotes have been very lightly edited for readability. All themes were well supported across interviews.

“It’s the data, dummies”

Interviewees repeatedly emphasized the importance of access to well-organized data and familiarity with the database taxonomies. P5 described data access as a key asset that BERIL co-scientist enabled:

“You have access to all these pipelines natively and all this data natively. And so it’s kind of just an incubator of exploring hypotheses because you have all—you have everything, you have all the pieces....”

Knowing what data is available where, knowing its quality, and knowing how to connect it were deemed critical to quickly getting trustworthy outputs from the co-scientist. P11 made it clear that data is the foundational asset that determines the utility of an AI agent for science:

“It's the data, dummies, you know, it really needs good data, right?....So if you don't have good quality, reliable, uniformly processed data that you can trust, then it's going to be a limitation, a big limitation.”

People who had the data they needed to pursue their research question, either because it was already available in the KBase lakehouse or because they brought it in themselves, generally enjoyed a successful workday. P1 provides one such example, also emphasizing the importance of being able to connect and harmonize multiple data sources. P1 was able to connect their own data to data they accessed with the co-scientist using a common taxonomy they were familiar with. P1 had a successful day and they credit their well-organized data: “I knew how to organize it so that it could find those connections. It found those connections. It gave me a good story.”

Some workshop attendees did not make it as far in their work as P1, spending more time looking for appropriate data to answer their research questions. This was sometimes difficult for them, especially because they felt they needed some familiarity with the data to leverage it properly. Interviewees like P2 wished the co-scientist could help them explore and inspect data more adeptly, “getting a description of what's in each table and looking at a few sample rows from each table.”

Supporting and aligning with mental models

Interviewees shared many thoughts about wishing the co-scientist would explain its choices more, being overwhelmed by outputs, wishing there were a checklist for the research steps, wishing they could have more check-ins and previews of the data. Through these requests, we recognize an opportunity to support users in maintaining a mental model of the co-scientist's research process. With a stronger mental representation of what the co-scientist was doing and when and why it was doing it, interviewees felt they would be better able to judge the quality of its work. Moreover, the BERIL co-scientist can better align its own processes to align with users' established mental models.

By providing more scaffolding to guide interactions with the co-scientist and monitor its work, BERIL can reduce feelings of being overwhelmed and make it easier to track progress. P9, for example, suggested the co-scientist could take a more iterative approach so that their “brain can hold it.” They said that the co-scientist had “gotten too fast” and they needed it to slow down and justify its choices: “Explain to me again, why did you ask? I've lost control.” Participants also noted that frequent requests from the co-scientist to grant it permissions (e.g., for downloading something) left them with alert fatigue. Because they were desensitized to the co-scientists' persistent and trivial questions, they were sometimes unsure if they had missed more important

information. In these cases of overwhelm and fatigue, users were unable to maintain an accurate mental model of the research process because it was occluded behind dense outputs.

Notably, by supporting better mental models of the research process and increasing users' engagement with the co-scientist, dreaded rework might be avoided. Interviewees wanted to avoid needing to redo work down the line. P7 expressed this idea: "It would be great if they can have more intermediate steps to ask you if this is what you want rather than just generate the whole thing and then you probably have to redirect them later."

To maintain awareness of progress and ensure its quality, interviewees wanted ways to check in on the data and results. With these check-ins, users would be able to better understand the co-scientist's actions and interpret its work. P8 described the interactions they imagined:

"I would like it to, at like the specific research steps, to stop and say, like, 'Here's the first plot, the first analysis that you asked for. What do you think of it? Like, what do you think of— do you want to look at the code? And then do you want to look at the plot?'"

Other people indicated that their usual research process without the co-scientist would include more opportunities for monitoring. P3 explained that they would usually explore the data and apply scrutiny more than they did during the time-bound challenge, preferring to do more exploratory work than the co-scientist allowed for. They said that the co-scientist created several formal hypotheses faster than P3 would have themselves; "I'm generally of the opinion that you want to see something that works before you start hypothesizing about where it can be pushed." They further explained that the co-scientist took over the initial data exploration, whereas P3 would usually do that themselves, "doing quite a lot of experimentation...to see what the data is reasonably capable of telling me." Absent these opportunities for exploration, interviewees had a poorer understanding of how the study was progressing. Additionally, these quotes show that the scientists found the co-scientist's approach to be out of sync with their established mental models of how research should proceed.

Seeking cues about what to trust

Some workshop participants asserted that the BERIL co-scientist is "like the most productive intern you could ever have" (P5) and that they could write "brilliant, amazing" manuscripts with it (P1), but many interviewees needed more clues to help them calibrate their trust in the AI agent's outputs. Sometimes the co-scientist used data or statistical techniques that interviewees were unfamiliar with, making it difficult for them to determine their trustworthiness.

A common request that could help users better calibrate their trust in the co-scientist was to be able to preview data and results, as P3 and P8 described above in *Supporting and aligning with mental models*. P11 also discussed this issue, providing an example of why the ability to inspect data is necessary:

"If you look at the group comparison... of things that had [a particular] enzyme and things that don't, the question would be, 'Am I data limited before I do that, right?'... Do I only have like 2 genomes that are [negative]? I couldn't do a

statistical test if I didn't know that, right? So I'd want to— so visually looking at it might be helpful.”

Uncertainty arose from more than the need to interrogate data, however. Interviewees explained that the co-scientist was sometimes confidently wrong, projecting unwarranted authority. The co-scientist didn't provide cues like tone and hedging that humans usually give to indicate uncertainty.

Absent better signals of how trustworthy the agent's work was, interviewees often relied on their own intuition to make judgements about quality, often moving on without deep investigation. As P6 noted: “I rarely review the exact Python scripts that it's giving me.”

Providing a specialized value proposition

Most interviewees (and workshop attendees) reported using AI daily for research tasks like ideation, experimental design and execution, writing, etc. Thus, despite the rapidly changing landscape of AI tooling, many participating BER researchers had already established preferred tools and expectations of AI agents. This meant that interviewees often compared the BERIL co-scientist to their usual AI tooling—often Anthropic's Claude or Claude Code. P5 appreciated the co-scientist's approach, stating that they feel “Claude is more hectic” and the co-scientist needed less steering.

Sometimes these comparisons were unfavorable for the BERIL co-scientist, signalling opportunities for its improvement. P10, for example, noted during a brief interview at the workshop that the co-scientist did not ask them as many questions as their locally installed and configured Claude instance does:

“It really wasn't asking questions, it was just, ‘Here's what I think’... And I think when working with just my own Claude instance, I've also set it up and prompted it in a way that I tell it to ask me clarifying questions and kind of critique its work before it gives it to me.”

The comparisons that interviewees made to other AI tools indicate that scientific agents like the BERIL co-scientist must provide a specialized value proposition. By seamlessly integrating the KBase data lakehouse with compute and other resources, BERIL can stand out against general-purpose tools. As more data are added to the lakehouse, this distinction will grow, helping to avoid scenarios like P4's, who was unable to access the data they needed, and therefore questioned why they would need the specialized agent:

“It turned out for my question that I ended up needing to download a lot of the data, almost all the data. So it was something that I could have done on Claude Code. And just because I'm more used to that and it's like something that's more user-friendly in some ways in this version of this, I was like, ‘Oh man, I think I could have done this in Claude more easily.’”

Interviewees' sentiments show that the BERIL co-scientist and other specialized scientific agents like it must deliver features and a user experience that offer unique advantages over generic alternatives.

Discussion

Even at this early stage, pairing curated data and compute (via the KBase Lakehouse) with a co-scientist (via BERIL) shows how substantially AI agents could change how researchers work. Aside from the feedback and findings reviewed above, we also heard promising reviews that the co-scientist enabled researchers to think “more about the science rather than debugging the code” (P6), directing their attention to more interesting research tasks. Yet, our interviews also show we have many lessons to learn before scientists can fully rely on AI assistants.

The mental models that dominate scientific reasoning and investigation are not always aligned with agent processes, even when launched in systems that support full provenance tracking with transparent recording of agent reasoning traces. Indeed, our interviews indicate that scientists struggled with the relatively linear pipeline that the BERIL co-scientist employed, feeling more comfortable with an iterative approach that would allow them to maintain a clearer view of their progress and output quality. Other qualities of AI agent-based co-scientists further drive the need to enable researchers' commonly explorative approach to science. Agents—even those like BERIL that are trained not to be sycophantic—have a tendency to present polished-looking results with complete confidence regardless of their accuracy. Scientists must be able to collaborate with agentic co-scientists in a way that allows them to interrogate outputs throughout the research process, engaging in their usual and often messy workflows.

Interviewees mentioned that they often took the co-scientist's work for granted, rather than engaging in verification. Scientists tended to accept plausible-looking results and to scrutinize only when something felt wrong—an efficient heuristic that is also a form of confirmation bias, and a route by which a confident error can pass into a published result. The design challenge is therefore to make verification the path of least resistance rather than an act of discipline, without slowing scientists down. The goal would be to surface the checkpoints that matter, at the moments they matter, instead of burying them in raw traces.

This approach will require flexibility as well; what is a useful checkin for some users may not be for others. Some researchers may want to investigate code blocks written by agents before running them or to deep dive into analytical decision making, while others will need to trust the co-scientist is doing what they need it to do and would rather be provided with explanations of what the agent is going to do and why. Agentic co-scientists like BERIL should provide flexible pathways for verification that suit researchers' varied skillsets and *a priori* degrees of trust in the co-scientist. Multiple mechanisms to encourage engagement rather than blind acceptance are critical.

As workshop attendees stated, a key asset that the BERIL co-scientist provided was integration of different data sources. This powerful resource accelerated many workshop attendees' efforts,

allowing them to rapidly answer questions or demonstrate a proof-of-concept. Data access sets BERIL apart from other AI agents, and adding datasets to the KBase Lakehouse should strengthen this advantage. Our workshop analysis shows that another key aspect of the co-scientist is the user experience; it must support researchers' preferred workflows and enable them to maintain a mental model of the agents' work.

Limitations

The analyses presented in this paper represent one facet of our investigation into users' experience with the BERIL co-scientist. Analysis of the system logs and survey data is ongoing, and interview data will continue to be analyzed as results from the other data sources are captured. While the multiple data sources will test and extend our findings, offering more depth and clarity, these initial interview results provide a useful preview of workshop attendees' experiences and establish important context for interpreting the quantitative data. Because these findings come from interviews, they capture what scientists said about their experience rather than what they did. For example, activity logs will provide quantitative metrics that pair with reported behaviors, such as how often outputs went uninspected.

Notably, the workshop was only held for one day, creating an artificial deadline that may have influenced participants' behavior and reactions. One participant expressed hesitation to intervene with the co-scientist's work because they were curious about how it would work on its own. While the format may have influenced how attendees worked with the co-scientist, it also pushed them to engage with the co-scientist at all steps of the research process from hypothesis to reporting, offering valuable insights. Additionally, interviewees indicated that the speed with which you can work with the co-scientist was an asset, suggesting that an accelerated research timeline may become typical when working with co-scientist agents. The one-day challenge may have sharpened some behaviors, including the rush to results, the impatience with permission prompts, and the readiness to accept outputs unchecked. Future work should explore how users' perceptions of the co-scientist evolve over time and any ways in which users adapt their workflows to this new mode of work.

Workshop attendees were self-selected, likely indicating their interest in using AI agents and willingness to explore new technologies. This limits our results to the exploration of behaviors and attitudes of early adopters (vs. AI skeptics). However, as a community of researchers interested in using AI co-scientists, this report provided an open forum for frank and constructive discussion that can help improve the tools and the user experience. And, the primary analyst has no long-term affiliation with BERIL or KBase.

Finally, we studied a single co-scientist at one moment in a fast-moving field, so specific frictions may not transfer to other systems, or to BERIL as it develops, even as the broader questions about the human-agent interaction likely will.

Conclusion

The BERIL co-scientist is a new AI agent that can access BER data and compute resources and collaborate with scientists as they pursue a research question, develop and execute a plan, and interpret results. Through interviews about a one-day workshop where researchers worked with the co-scientist, we learned about user experience needs: scientists need visibility into the co-scientists' process so that they can create a mental model of its work; they also need better alignment with their own mental models of the research process, fewer trivial permissions requests, stronger cues to help them evaluate trustworthiness, the ability to explore data more in depth, and a value proposition that sets the agent apart from generic alternatives. Analytical power alone does not determine the success of AI agents for science; what matters is how well an AI co-scientist can help scientists judge when to delegate and when to verify. To drive adoption and further improve usability, the BERIL team will work to meet users where they are, developing new ways to help users determine what to trust. Importantly, workshop attendees found the co-scientist capable of planning and executing analyses – agent capabilities were not the primary impediment to accelerated, high quality science. Instead, friction arose as human users attempted to maintain oversight and assess trustworthiness.

Funding statement

The Biological and Environmental Research Intelligence Layer (BERIL) is funded by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, Office of Biological and Environmental Research under Award Numbers DE-AC02-05CH11231, DE-AC02-06CH11357, and DE-AC05-00OR22725.

The DOE Systems Biology Knowledgebase (KBase) is funded by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, Office of Biological and Environmental Research under Award Numbers DE-AC02-05CH11231, DE-AC02-06CH11357, DE-AC05-00OR22725, and DE-SC0012704.

Cphoon's work is supported by the High Performance Data Facility (HPDF) through the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science under contracts 89243126CSC000213 (JLab) and DE-AC02-05CH11231 (LBNL).

References

1. Gottweis J, Weng WH, Daryin A, Tu T, Sirkovic P, Myaskovsky A, et al. Accelerating scientific discovery with Co-Scientist. *Nature*. 2026 May 19; <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41586-026-10644-y>
2. Ghareeb AE, Chang B, Mitchener L, Yiu A, Szostkiewicz CJ, Shved D, et al. A multi-agent system for automating scientific discovery. *Nature*. 2026 May 19; <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/s41586-026-10652-y>
3. Ledford H. Teams of AI agents boost speed of research. *Nature*. 2026 May 19; <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/d41586-026-01596-4>
4. Roberts KF, Abrams ZB, Cappelletti L, Moqri M, Heugel N, Caufield JH, et al. OpenScientist: evaluating an open agentic AI co-scientist to accelerate biomedical discovery. *medRxiv*. medRxiv; 2026. <http://dx.doi.org/10.64898/2026.03.15.26348338>
5. Yamada Y, Lange RT, Lu C, Hu S, Lu C, Foerster J, et al. The AI Scientist-v2: Workshop-level automated scientific discovery via agentic tree search. *arXiv [cs.AI]*. 2025. <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2504.08066>
6. Why AI cannot do good science without humans. *Nature*. 2026 May;653(8115):650. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-026-01551-3>
7. Luo Z, Kasirzadeh A, Shah NB. The more you automate, the less you see: Hidden pitfalls of AI scientist systems. *arXiv [cs.AI]*. 2025. <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2509.08713>
8. Wang D, Cheng M, Yu S, Liu Z, Guo Z, Li X, et al. PaperArena: An evaluation benchmark for tool-augmented agentic reasoning on scientific literature. *arXiv [cs.AI]*. 2025. <http://dx.doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2510.10909>
9. Jones N. Human scientists trounce the best AI agents on complex tasks. *Nature*. 2026 Apr;652(8111):841–2. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/d41586-026-01199-z>
10. Lee JD, See KA. Trust in automation: designing for appropriate reliance. *Hum Factors*. 2004 Spring;46(1):50–80. http://dx.doi.org/10.1518/hfes.46.1.50_30392
11. Venkatesh V, Bala H. Technology acceptance model 3 and a research agenda on interventions. *Decis Sci*. 2008 May;39(2):273–315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5915.2008.00192.x>
12. Braun V, Clarke V. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qual Res Psychol*. 2006 Jan;3(2):77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>